

Tips and tricks for the new Oxford Nanopore MinION user for plant genome sequencing: a short technical note

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Abstract. *In the last decade a growing number of plant genomes have been obtained for species previously considered as non model species, thanks to the development of long read sequencing. The availability of bench sequencing devices such as the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) MinION has opened the way for in house sequencing in many labs. In this short technical note we aim at providing a few tips for handling the plant material, performing the DNA extraction, libraries preparation and sequencing run on a MinION platform. We further describe basic steps in obtaining a high quality base calling, delivering quality control metrics, visualizing the data with IGV and detecting structural variants if a reference genome is available. We hope this will be useful for colleagues interested in population genomics and in the discovery of structural variants in a variety of plant species.*

Keywords: Oxford Nanopore Technologies, plant genome sequencing, long reads

A. Material and Methods

Reagents

- Carlson lysis buffer (2% CTAB, 100 mM Tris-HCl pH 9,5, 20 mM EDTA pH 8, 1.4 M NaCl, 1% PEG 8000)
- 2-mercaptoethanol
- RNase A
- Qiagen blood and cell culture DNA mini kit (Qiagen, ref. 13323) or Genomic DNA clean & concentrator-10 kit (Zymo research, ref. D4011)
- « 2X size selection buffer » (2.5% w/v PVP 360000, 1.2 M NaCl, 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8).
- Agencourt AMPure XP beads Beckmann coulter A63880
- NEBNext® Companion Module for Oxford Nanopore Technologies® Ligation Sequencing (ref. E7180S). Alternatively, you can purchase NEB reagents individually:
 - NEBNext® FFPE Repair Mix (ref. M6630)
 - NEBNext® End repair / dA-tailing Module (ref. E7546)
 - NEBNext® Quick Ligation Module (ref. E6056)
- 1.5 ml Eppendorf DNA LoBind tubes (Eppendorf, ref. 022431021)
- 0.2 ml thin-walled PCR tubes or SARSTEDT Multiply® µstrip 0.2 ml chain (ref. 72.985.002) and lid chain flat (ref. 65.989.002)
- Nuclease-free water (e.g. ThermoFisher, ref. AM9937)
- Freshly prepared 70% ethanol in nuclease-free water
- Qubit 1X dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Invitrogen ref. Q33231)
- ONT flowcells: FLO-MIN106D (R9.4.1) or FLO-MIN111 (R10.3)

Figure 1. Overview of the wet lab (A) and computational analyses (B) from the plant material to the visualization of the MinION long read data (when a reference genome is available).

Equipment

- Hula mixer (gentle rotator mixer)
- Magnetic rack DynaMag™ 2 (ref 12321D)
- Microfuge
- Vortex mixer
- Thermal cycler at 20°C and 65°C
- P1000, P200, P100, P20, P10 and P2 pipette and tips
- Ice bucket with ice
- Timer
- Qubit fluorimeter
- Spectrophotometer NanoDrop™ 2000
- MinION sequencing platform (or Mk1B)

Softwares

- MinION Software Release 21.11.8 (<https://community.nanoporetech.com/downloads>)
- Guppy v6.0.1 (<https://community.nanoporetech.com/downloads>)
- minimap2 (<https://github.com/lh3/minimap2>)
- samtools (<https://github.com/samtools/>)
- Sniffles2 (<https://github.com/fritzsedlazeck/Sniffles>)
- IGV (<https://software.broadinstitute.org/software/igv/download>)

Computational hardware

- GPU system (example): Memory 62,5 GiB, Processor Intel® Xeon(R) W-2265 CPU @ 3.50GHz ×24, Graphic card NVIDIA Corporation TU104 [GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER] / NVIDIA Corporation TU104 [GeForce RTX 2080 SUPER], Disk capacity 2,5 TB

- CPU system (example): Memory 15,5 GiB, Processor Intel® Core™ i7-7700 CPU @ 3.60GHz ×8, Graphic card Mesa Intel® HD Graphics 630 (KBL GT2), Disk capacity 1,0 TB

Below we detail the protocol we used for wet lab and in silico steps (**Figure 1**).

B. Wet lab protocol

1. Preparing plant material

1.1 Harvesting a single plant is preferred if to increase the chance of discovering segregating structural variants in a population. Although we initially tried to maintain the plants for a couple of days in the dark before harvesting in order to reduce the number of chloroplasts, we have found that this step is not needed. A quantity between 0.6 and 1 g is required for the gDNA extraction, however it is possible to start from 0.25 g of material (adapting the protocols to the initial quantity) and pool the samples afterwards, if needed. For precious material we do not recommend to pool the tissues, as the QC metrics of the extraction can vary. Pooling the extractions after QC is preferred. Plant materials used in this study were grown in a growth chamber in soil under a 16h/8h (light/dark) cycle (*Arabidopsis thaliana*, petunia); in a greenhouse (*Oryza sativa*) or harvested in the field (chestnut tree, common ivy, *Delphinium* see Salvado et al. 2022).

1.2 Material can be stored at -80°C. Avoid thaw/freeze cycles.

2. Performing DNA extraction

2.1 Extract genomic DNA from plant material using Carlson extraction method (Carlson lysis buffer (2% CTAB, 100 mM Tris-HCl pH 9,5, 20 mM EDTA pH 8, 1.4 M NaCl, 1% PEG 8000), 0.25% 2-mercaptoethanol, 0,2 % RNase A).

2.2 Perform a chloroform extraction, recover the supernatant using a P1000 cut tip to preserve long fragments.

2.3 Precipitate the nucleic acids with isopropanol (0.7 v/v) and resuspend in 50 µl of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8).

2.4 Purify the nucleic acids using the Qiagen blood and cell culture DNA mini kit, following the manufacturer's instructions.

Note: *Alternatively a CTAB extraction method can be used (CTAB buffer (2% W/V CTAB (cetyl trimethylammonium bromide), 100 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 20 mM EDTA pH 8, 1.4 M NaCl, 0.2% 2-mercaptoethanol, 0.05% N lauryol sodium sarcosyl). For samples with a high secondary metabolite or sugar content we recommend the protocole developed for poplar from Pushkova et al, 2019. For the purification step, columns can be used (Genomic DNA clean & concentrator-10 kit, Zymo research). However the columns can be tricky to manipulate (difficulty to recover the sample) and lead to some DNA loss. In our hands the Carlson method coupled with the Qiagen purification kit improved the overall read length, compared to the CTAB method coupled with Zymo columns (Figure 2).*

3. Performing DNA preparation quality control

3.1 Visualize the DNA quality by migrating on an 0.8% agarose gel.

3.2 Measure the DNA concentration using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer. We expect a concentration > 100 ng/µl and ratios for 260/280 ~ 2,2 and 260/230 ~ 1,8, respectively.

3.3 Measure the DNA concentration using a Qubit fluorometer and the Qubit 1X dsDNA HS Assay Kit. Minimum concentration should be 100 ng/µl.

Figure 2. Impact of the DNA extraction method on MinION read length and yield. Violin plots showing the obtained read length (A, reads N50) and gigabases of pass reads (B, Gb pass) for the samples obtained from an extraction using the Carlson buffer and CTAB buffer, respectively. The species are color coded on both panels, as indicated.

Note: We consider that a DNA preparation is suitable for sequencing if the ratios between the Nanodrop measurement and the Qubit measurement do not exceed 2 fold (Nanodrop conc./Qubit conc. < 2). If the DNA is too diluted or the quantity is too poor we recommend pooling the samples and performing an ethanol acetate precipitation, using cut p200 tips. For this add 1/10 volume Na acetate (1M, pH8) and 2,5 volumes of cold EtOH 100%. Rinse with 2 volumes of EtOH 75%. Dry under a laminar flow hood for 2 hours and resuspend in 50 µl of TE, at 4°C O/N. Then repeat the QC (3.2, 3.3).

4. Preparing library and sequencing run

4.1 We used the following kits for library preparation: SQK-LSK109 and SQK-LSK110. No difference could be noted on the yield or N50 (not shown). Prepare the libraries following the ONT protocole. For size selection step: prepare a dilution at 100 ng/µl in a maximum volume of 60 µl and

prepare a home made « 2X size selection buffer » (2.5% w/v PVP 360000 1.2 M NaCl, 20 mM Tris.HCl, pH 8).

4.2 The runs were performed with a MinION Flow Cell (R9.4.1) using MinKNOW version 3.6.5 to 4.3.12.

4.3 Perform updates and restart your PC. Check that the PC has enough free space.

4.4 Perform flow cell quality control. Insert flow cell in the MinION and run « check ».

Figure 3. Impact of the quantity of library deposited on the flow cell on the yield. Graph showing the obtained gigabases of pass reads (Gb pass) according to the library input (in µg). The species are color coded as indicated on the right.

Note: For libraries: We typically prepare the libraries from 2 to 3.5 µg of gDNA. The total amount of input library (in µg) loaded on the flow cell has a positive impact on the yield (Figure 3). For the flow cells: customers

are required to perform a flow cell check within 3 months of purchase, as defective flow cells can be replaced. Problems encountered with the MinKNOW interface can be solved by updating the MinKNOW version, or alternately by writing to the community (<https://community.nanoporetech.com>) or the ONT Customer Services (support@nanoporetech.com). If the run would stop while sequencing (power cut), the user can simply restart the PC and launch again the run without touching the flow cell. Concerning the choice of the flow cells, while R9 flow cells can be chosen for a higher yield, R10 should be considered for a higher N50 (**Figure 4**). The flow cells R10 are recommended for the Q20+ ligation kit (not used here). However, currently, for DNA methylation analysis, R9 flow cells are recommended. The runs (performed in 2019-2022) produced 240,000 to 2 Giga reads pass and 1 to 11,8 Gb of pass reads, with a N50 ranging from 5 to 33 Kb. During the run, while the total number of pores has an impact on the yield, the number of simultaneous sequencing pores had no clear impact (**Figure 5**).

Figure 4. Impact of the flow cell type on MinION read length and yield. Violin plots showing the obtained read length (A, reads N50 in kb) and gigabases of pass reads (B, Gb pass) for the R10 and R9 flow cell types, respectively. The species are color coded on both panels, as indicated.

Figure 5. Impact of the number of sequencing pores and total pores of the flow cell on the yield. Graphs showing the obtained gigabases of pass reads (Gb pass) for the sequencing pores (A) and total pores of the flow cell (B). The species are color coded on both panels, as indicated.

C. Basic bioanalysis

1. Accurate base calling (Guppy)

1.1 Performing fast base calling during the run is possible.

1.2 The reads can be further basecalled on a GPU machine using Guppy in hac (high quality) mode (version 3.2.10 to 5.0.16), using the command line as follows:

```
$ /ont-guppy/bin/guppy_basecaller -i /fast5/ -s flowcell_number_data -c /opt/ont/guppy/data/dna_r9.4.1_450bps_hac.cfg -x "cuda:0"
```

2. Quality metrics

2.1 Concatenate the fastq files:

```
$ cat *.fastq > all_hac_flowcell_number.fastq
```

2.2 Use NanoComp (for one to several runs) with the following command line:

```
$ NanoComp -t 8 --fastq all_hac_flowcell_number.fastq --names flowcell_number -f pdf --outdir path_to_outdir_file
```

3. Mapping on a reference genome

3.1 Open the terminal (on a Linux or a macOS machine).

3.2 Download the sequence file (.fasta) and gene/transposon annotation (.gff3, .gff or .gtf) of your reference genome of interest.

3.3 Map the fastq sequencing data on your reference genome as follows:

```
# mapping
```

```
$ minimap2 -ax map-ont genome.fasta all_hac_flowcell_number.fastq > minimap_ONT.sam
```

```
# converting files
```

```
$ samtools view -S -b minimap_ONT.sam > minimap_ONT.bam
```

```
$ samtools flagstat minimap_ONT.bam
```

```
$ samtools sort minimap_ONT.bam -o minimap_ONT.sorted.bam
```

```
# indexing
```

```
$ samtools index minimap_ONT.sorted.bam
```

4. Detecting structural variants (SVs)

4.1 Use Sniffles2 with the following command line:

```
sniffles -i minimap_ONT.sorted.bam -v output.vcf
```

5. Visualizing the data on IGV

5.1 Open IGV

Genomes> Load genome from File (choose your fasta reference genome file)

File> Load from File (choose your .sorted.bam alignment file)

File> Load from File (choose your .gff annotation file)

5.2 Calculate the coverage

Tools > Run igvtools > Input file (choose your .sorted.bam alignment file) > Change window size (e.g. 10000, for a coverage on 10kb windows).

On the main IGV window, right click on the first track and add the .tdf file using « Load precomputed coverage ».

5.3 Visualise SVs by loading the vcf file.

Note: ONT genome sequencing can be used to detect SV and, for small genomes (e.g. *A. thaliana*), can even be used to confirm the presence of small indels and SNPs if their respective position is known. Indeed, despite the high level of error rate when using R9 or R10 flow cells with the LSK109, LSK110 kits, the homozygous mutations can be detected non ambiguously. For example CRISPR-induced mutations can be confirmed (not shown).

Authors' contribution

CL designed the study. CL elaborated the protocols and performed the experiments. CL and MM analysed the data, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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